

First record of *Trechoblemus micros* (Herbst, 1784) in Bulgaria (Coleoptera: Carabidae: Trechini)

Borislav GUÉORGUIEV

A trip to the Rushovata peshtera Cave realised on 7th of May 2004 by Dr. Petar Beron yielded three cave-dwelling trechid species: *Trechoblemus micros* (Herbst, 1784) (2 males, 1 female), *Trechus* (*Trechus*) *austriacus* Dejean, 1831 (6 males, 10 females), and *Trechus* (*Trechus*) *irenis* Csiki, 1912 (2 males). The cave is situated in Triassic limestone (Vasilyovski Karst Region), lying close to village of Gradeshnitsa, Central Predbalkan. The beetles were found near the riverbank, in moist habitat, among a mixture of debris and remnants of plants. The genus *Trechoblemus* Ganglbauer, 1892 with *T. micros* have so far unknown on the territory of Bulgaria that is why a short diagnosis is provided here. It could be distinguished from the other representatives of the tribe Trechini in Bulgaria by the following set of characters: penultimate labial palpomere with 4 setae, eyes present, entire upper surface of body finely punctate and pubescent, and the apical stria of elytron joining stria

Fig. 1. *Trechoblemus micros*, lateral aspect of median lobe. Scale line = 0.1 mm

3. Median lobe: as illustrated on Fig. 1. APFELBECK (1904, Familienreihe Caraboidea, Berlin, R. Friedländer & Sohn), having at disposal material collected from Bosnia, first recorded *Trechoblemus micros* in the Balkan Peninsula. Later MATITS (1922, Spomenik srpske kraljevske akademije, 57) announced it from Serbia. A review of the species distribution in the west part of Balkans, including Slovenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Serbia can be found in DROVENIK & PEKS (1999, Schwanfelder Coleopterologische Mitteilungen, Neuauflage Sonderheft, 1). The species is widespread in the whole Euro-Siberian region. Along with the other records from Asturia (Spain), Bosnia, Turkey and Adzharia (Georgia), the Bulgarian locality forms the southern border of species areal. According to CASALE & LANEYRIE (1983, Mémoires de Biospéologie, 9) the genus *Trechoblemus* includes six species: one in the

Nearctics, four in East Asia, and the Euro-Siberian *T. micros*. The genus belongs to one of the oldest phyletic lineages of tribe Trechini in the Northern Hemisphere (JEANNEL, 1928, L'Abeille, 35), showing excessively disjunctive Holarctic distribution. This lineage has its highest diversity of genera and species in East Asia and eastern part of the USA. Besides, one genus with six species, as well as two genera with three species are known from the Carpathians and the Tian Shan Range, respectively. Worth species mention is the present distribution of genus *Pseudanophthalmus* Jeannel, 1920 (= *Duvaliopsis* Jeannel, 1928), which representatives occur in two regions – the southeastern part of North America and the Carpathian Range in Europe. This type of distribution is probably a result of Eocene-Oligocene land (faunal) connections between North America and Europe (NOONAN, 1988, Memoirs of the Entomological Society of Canada, 144).